

Focus groups 2: protocol

Background

The [Book Analytics Dashboard \(BAD\) Project](#) (Curtin/OAPEN/Educopia 2022-2025) is engaging in product development work in Q4 2022 in order to support OAPEN's work to identify stakeholders, create personas, develop value propositions, and test those with prospective clients/members.

To help achieve these goals, we hosted focus groups in 2023. These focus group sessions were designed to simultaneously orient stakeholders to the technical product and test the product's readiness for purpose for scholarly publishers of varied sizes and forms, as well as other high-potential future clients (e.g., funders).

As part of this work, the team hosted its first focus group sessions in Q1 2023 with three core stakeholder groups: 1) Commercial publishers, 2) University Presses, and 3) Library Publishers. Additional focus groups, including those with other stakeholder groups, will be pursued later in the project period.

Virtual Focus Group Protocol

Purpose

These Focus Groups were designed to collect input, share progress, and test stakeholder ideas and perspectives regarding the Book Analytics Dashboard prototypes and the emerging legal and financial framework we are building to support this product. Meeting design and facilitation were provided by Educopia Institute (initial design, documentation, and script; notetaking) and OAPEN (refined design and script, lead facilitation).

Script

Good morning/afternoon! The date is [DATE]. Thank you for your participation in this focus group, hosted by OAPEN on behalf of the Book Analytics Dashboard project, a Mellon-funded initiative of Curtin University, OAPEN, and Educopia. My name is [NAME 1] and I am the [TITLE/ROLE]. I will be moderating today's focus group, alongside my colleague, [NAME 2], who will observe and take notes for us.

This focus group is designed to gather your feedback and input about the design and utility of our prototype book analytics dashboard. The conversation we're going to have together over the next 90 minutes will focus your collective energy and attention where it is most needed today: on the product itself, and also on how you all would advise us to pursue our remaining product development work as we move from pilot to production in order to best serve the needs of [GROUP TYPE].

Audio of this focus group will be recorded and possibly transcribed. We will use the recording and possible transcription solely to support our project efforts. If the project team ever considers any other uses, we would reach out to you beforehand to obtain your informed consent.

With that understanding, do you consent to today's focus group being recorded? Do you have any questions about the process? Please signal your willingness to participate in this recorded focus group by stating "yes" in the chat window.

Communications and important links

- [link to methodology including invitation email]
- [link to slides]

Pework

We will provide the [BAD Template Dashboard](#) to focus group participants a week prior to their session and ask them to spend 15 min with the templates and answer a very short set of questions (forthcoming pre-work assessment) that draw their attention to specific features.

Session Instructions

1. Welcome (slides 1-2), 3 min
2. Question 1: Introductions: name, organization, childhood book (slide 3), allow 1 min per participant, should be on "orientation" by 10 after ideally.
3. Orientation, Demo (slides 4-9), 3 minutes tops
 - a. Very brief project intro
 - b. Data sources
 - c. Remind them this is explicitly not-for-profit, governed by stakeholders, not lock-in heavy
 - d. Initial review of dashboard format
 - i. Current template dashboard on prototyping phase: template.book-analytics.org/
4. Question 2: Have you used dashboards for business intel in the past? Which ones? (gauge group familiarity, identify different products folks are familiar with) (slide 10)
5. Question 3: What could you accomplish with these dashboards that would further your own efforts? (slide 11)
 - a. What problem(s) are they looking for this to solve, or what opportunities do they think a dashboard will help them pinpoint? Will this save them time they're expending now trying to gather this info for themselves, or will it be altogether new for them?
6. Features review (slides 12-14)

You've seen the template dashboards and we want you to draw on your memory of that experience now.

Based on what you saw and experienced:

- a. Question 4: Which features are essential and which are desirable? Why?
 - i. Polling (informal) for beta features
- b. Question 5: What features are we missing currently that you feel are important?
 - i. Gauge consistency or lack thereof
 - ii. Prioritize this list if possible
- c. Question 6: Who from your team will be the primary user(s) of the dashboards?
 - i. Main purpose of the question is to see what job titles/range of folks they expect will need access and want access
 - ii. Capture names where possible for future survey/community work

7. Business model review (slides 15-18)
 - a. Question 7: The product offering could be set up with standard/premium services or standard/à la carte services. Initial perceptions of each?
 - i. Capture list
 - b. Question 8: What pricing range would you expect for the service? Could you begin paying for this service in 2023? 2024? How much lead time do you need?
 - i. Capture anything they'll give us, try for #s
 - c. Question 9: Who from your team will be involved in the signing of legal agreements?
 - i. Main purpose of the question is to see what job titles/range of folks they expect to be involved and how sensitive they think this is (what might the process look like for them)
 - ii. Capture names where possible
 - d. Question 10: What community governance qualities or characteristics would you want and expect for this service?
8. Concluding slide - webpage + links (slide 19)